

Studies on North Gangetic Deposits from Farraka (Bengal) to Mansi (Bihar) in India

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Twenty-three samples from North Gangetic belt starting from Farraka (Bengal) to Mansi (Bihar) in India have been analytically studied. The percentage composition of the constituents along with pH, swelling index, loss on ignition, bulk density etc. have been reported. The cation exchange capacity values have been found to vary from 4.45 to 18.42 m.e per 100 g. The water holding capacities determined at different temperatures (26° to 75°) have been recorded. The important observation that log of water holding capacity plotted against the inverse of absolute temperature results in the straight line, has been reported; this type of observation is not available in the literature with other soil samples studied.

THE properties and chemical behaviours of some different river deposits have been studied¹⁻⁶.

North Gangetic river belt is not a permanent belt and whenever the course of river changes the old soil deposits from various points mixing in very very dilute aqueous medium are carried to some other points as new deposits. The study of these deposits appears to have not been done in order to throw light on the characteristics of regular and irregular deposits by the river Ganges. In addition to the chemical and physical properties of the soil samples of a particular region we have undertaken to study the water holding capacity at different temperatures.

Experimental

Twenty-three soil samples collected from 0-20 cm depth from different places from northern Gangetic belt starting from Farraka (Bengal) to Mansi (Bihar) in summer of 1975 before flood by BNS and MMP were taken for investigations. The samples were dried in air oven for a few hours and then powdered to pass through 150 mesh sieve (0.104 mm). The powder samples were dried at 110-120° for 24 hours. The dried powder was kept in a closed desiccator and used for all determinations. These samples were analysed for definite chemico-physical properties following standard methods^{7,8}. The average percentage deviation in the determination of percentage of SiO₂, Al₂O₃ and Fe₂O₃ was found to be ±1.52 per cent, ±0.65 per cent and ±0.45 per cent respectively obtained from these determinations.

The C.E.C. values were obtained by treatment with standard K₂CO₃ solution following volumetric measurements against standard hydrochloric acid

solution⁹. These values with pH, swelling index, bulk density, loss on ignition and water holding capacity at 26±1 were obtained and recorded in Table 1. The deviation in cation exchange capacity in m.e per 100 g never exceeded ±0.46.

The water holding capacity of the soils were obtained at different temperatures (26 to 75°) and are recorded in Table 2. The log of water holding capacity is plotted against the inverse of absolute temperature and the straight lines obtained are shown in Fig. 1.

Results and Discussion

The percentage of SiO₂ in these samples is very high (74 to 84.65 p.c.) as is expected with the soil samples of these belts. It is interesting to note that the percentage of Al₂O₃ varying from 5.00 to 12.80 is nearly twice the percentage of Fe₂O₃ varying from 2.32 to 6.86 at both ends of the limit covering a big length from Farraka to Mansi (Vide Table 1). In almost all cases the percentage of carbon is more than the percentage of nitrogen resulting in the high value of C/N ratio to 31.20. The total percentage of phosphorous in these samples is very poor and in out of 23 samples studied nine gave just the qualitative positive test showing its presence in traces only.

Some of the soil samples of this belt are alkaline and some of them are acidic with a limit of pH from 8.1 to 6.5 further showing that these samples are neither strongly alkaline nor strongly acidic in character. The cation exchange capacity determined from standard K₂CO₃ solution varies from 4.45 to 18.42 m.e per 100 g. It is clear from these data

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that the cation exchange capacity of these soils is predominantly due to bivalent exchangeable cations, calcium ion (0.12 to 1.62 p.c.) has been reported to

TABLE 1—PHYSICO-CHEMICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE SOIL SAMPLES

Sl. No. ^x	Al ₂ O ₃ p.c.	Fe ₂ O ₃ p.c.	pH	C.E.C. m c/100 g	Capacity water holding at 26°
1	2	3	4	5	6
1.	6.32	4.86	6.50	10.52	40.25
2.	7.25	3.42	7.20	12.56	40.00
3.	12.44	6.86	6.60	18.42	55.25
4.	8.20	5.20	7.80	15.24	44.26
5.	10.85	5.00	7.50	10.20	25.98
6.	12.80	6.12	6.70	4.867	54.20
7.	8.02	4.02	7.10	8.10	60.25
8.	7.52	3.45	7.60	7.72	35.38
9.	12.22	6.68	8.00	15.52	36.42
10.	10.42	4.12	8.10	10.25	49.25
11.	8.62	3.82	7.20	8.26	52.50
12.	7.25	3.18	6.70	12.75	29.75
13.	7.25	3.02	7.40	4.85	26.00
14.	9.25	4.84	6.80	15.25	18.25
15.	5.25	3.86	7.20	10.20	39.45
16.	5.00	3.42	6.50	8.25	32.26
17.	11.46	3.50	7.70	12.26	16.35
18.	9.36	5.21	7.70	4.45	48.60
19.	9.00	3.10	6.60	5.37	42.95
20.	7.54	4.00	4.90	6.25	35.68
21.	7.12	2.32	7.80	9.12	31.75
22.	11.22	4.25	6.80	6.45	28.25
23.	9.30	3.84	6.90	12.68	42.65

x. Name of the places from where the samples were collected:
 1. Khajuria Ghat (Farraka North), 2. Manickchak (Maldah-W.B.), 3. Maharajpur diara (S.P.-Bihar), 4. Amdahad, 5. Naulakha, 6. Manihari diara (Katihar-Bihar), 7. Shobhanpur diara (S.P.-Bihar), 8. Bari Kodarjana diara (North), 9. Karbagola Ghat (Katihar-Bihar), 10. Tintanga, 11. Saidpur diara, 12. Mahadecpur Ghat, 13. Chawania, 14. Lattipur diara, 15. Chakfatma, 16. Gangapur diara (Bhagalpur-Bihar), 17. Korchakka-Bharat Khand, 18. Salarpur, 19. Agwani, 20. Thuthi Sirajpur, 21. Srinia diara, 22. Gogri diara, 23. Mansi (Monghyr).

Fig. 1. Plot of log of water holding capacities vs $\frac{1}{T}$

occur in the soil samples but no definite relation between the amount of bivalent cation and the C.E.C. values could be established, may be due to heterogeneous character of the soil samples of this belt. The p.c. of alkali oxide has been found to vary from 0.06 percent to 0.32 p.c. in most of the cases except for sample no. 23, 3 and 16 for which the values are respectively 0.62 p.c., 0.54 p.c. and 0.42 p.c. The swelling index of these samples does not vary much and the loss on ignition which includes the loss of the combined water and decomposable substances ranges from 5.25 to 8.60 p.c. The bulk density which is a measure of porosity at a particular temperature varies from 1.04 to 1.32.

The water holding capacity of these soils have been determined at different temperatures from 26° to 75°. With rise in temperature the values for water holding capacity have been found to decrease. Above 75° these values have been found to be erratic and meaningless. It has been tried to plot log of water holding capacity (H.C.) against the inverse of absolute temperature when straight line is obtained (vide Fig. 1). It is an important observation with the soils of this belt that the

straight line relation in between $\log H.C$ and $\frac{1}{T}$ holds good. It is interesting to note that the values of antilog of Y at $\frac{1}{T} = 25 \times 10^{-4} \text{ deg}^{-1}$ comes out to be equal to the percentage of $Fe_2O_3 + Al_2O_3$ obtained experimentally. The comparative values are tabulated in Table 2. In majority of the cases the

results are well comparable and in few cases wide variation noticeable may be due to structural differences. The water holding capacity of soil might depend on the composition of the soil and on increasing the temperature the texture of the soil may change resulting in the decrease of the water holding capacity. It is proposed that such physico-chemical studies of the deposits of river Ganges at regular intervals of time may reveal the nature of the chemical composition of the deposits when soluble and insoluble constituents in very dilute aqueous medium are carried from one place to other during erosion.

TABLE 2—PERCENTAGE OF $Fe_2O_3 + Al_2O_3$ FROM THE STRAIGHT LINE AT $\frac{1}{T} = 25 \times 10^{-4} \text{ deg}^{-1}$ (VIDE FIGURE 1)

Sl. No.	p.c. of $Fe_2O_3 + Al_2O_3$ from Table 1	p.c. of $Fe_2O_3 + Al_2O_3$ from straight line at $\frac{1}{T} = 25 \times 10^{-4} \text{ deg}^{-1}$
1	2	3
1.	11.18	10.00
2.	10.67	10.96
3.	19.30	10.00
4.	13.40	13.18
5.	15.85	14.79
6.	18.92	17.78
7.	12.04	12.59
8.	10.97	11.22
9.	18.90	15.84
10.	14.54	14.12
11.	12.44	11.22
12.	10.43	10.47
13.	10.54	11.22
14.	14.09	10.00
15.	9.11	9.63
16.	8.42	2.51
17.	11.96	2.40
18.	14.57	14.12
19.	12.10	12.59
20.	11.54	6.31
21.	9.44	4.47
22.	15.47	11.22
23.	13.14	8.91

References

1. BISWANATH DAS, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, **53**, 118.
2. S. K. DE, SHARAFAT ALI and K. C. GAUR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, **53**, 393.
3. G. SINGH, SHARAFAT ALI, D. PALIT and S. K. DE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, **53**, 407.
4. N. C. DEBNATH and S. K. BANERJEE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, **53**, 620.
5. BISWANATH DAS, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, **53**, 623.
6. SHARAFAT ALI and S. K. DE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, **53**, 934 and 1025.
7. S. K. DE, "Methods of Soil Analysis", Narayan Publishing House, Allahabad, 1963.
8. M. L. JACKSON, "Soil Chemical Analysis", Asia Publishing House, Bombay, 1958.
9. S. AMBI, N. K. JHA, M. M. PRASAD and BIVEKANAND MISHRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, **55**, 1077.